

Fractured Spaces: A Case Study of DeLillo's *White Noise* and *Cosmopolis*

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Abstract

This paper seeks to investigate the idea of spatiality and how it is crucially intertwined in the day to day subjective understanding of the world around, trying to understand the very dimensions of it, how it is formed, shaped and is changing continuously by the impact of globalization, capitalism, media culture, technological progress and other significant socio-cultural affects that imperiously threaten to change the course of our existence. Faced with the continuous incursion of technology, money capital, transmigration of labour and changing patterns of economy, how safe or precarious are we in this world? Pitted in the labyrinth of a consumer society and interlocked in the maze of a media society, how difficult is it to construe a sense of the 'self' in this 'fractured times' as Eric Hobsbawm would argue in his *The Age of Extremes*. This is the age of the highest state of postmodernism where we see the rise of late capitalism and a highly technocrat society erected on the scaffolds of the cyber world. We need to be skeptic of the 'space' in which such a tension is nettled. Unlike the modernists who were relentlessly scrutinizing the 'time'-the time of anxiety, the psychological affects of time linking it to memory, idealizing the time past and berating the time present, the attitude of the post modernist theorists is to be critical of the 'space' of this 'now'. The present paper will take up two very important novels of Don DeLillo namely *White Noise* and *Cosmopolis* wherein the aim will be to reveal this complex dynamics of spatial changes imbued with an understanding of the late capitalist world and how the nature of this impact is battled differently by the central protagonists of the two novels. That cities are a site of profound paradox is nowhere clear in these two novels, where urban areas simultaneously represent both

the frontiers of globalization as well as the deeply troubling social and political inequalities. While *White Noise* is about an impending fear of death, *Cosmopolis* is a more direct attack on the anxiety of living in a capitalist world where personal relationships are unstable and there is a catastrophic collision between the individual and the social. The thrust of the argument will be to investigate if such a geospatial understanding of the subject is at all possible in this continual time of instability and flux. The paper will seek to look at these issues critically.

Key words: De Lillo, labour, affects, cities, space.

The rhetoric of space and spatial consciousness is the new idiom that has infiltrated the field of social theory and has blended with the common parlance. "Space" has been traditionally given an inferior position in the sensibility- in geography as a presence which is just there outside us, in physics as the extraterrestrial zone outside the Earth and in mathematics in terms of area, substituting it easily with place. Space has been either delimited and boundaries are drawn on all sides to define its existence in the society around or it has been relegated as something unimportant or rather inferior as a subject of study.

The overarching concern that has grappled philosophers, thinkers, artists as well as scientists was the construction of "time," how time creates or shapes the Being and how this temporal nature of the world can be realized in the day to day experience with the world. Time was looked as the primogenitor of all forms of life as well as the overlord who has the power to destroy it. It became therefore imperative for philosophers to study the nature of this temporal and categorize it so as to facilitate our understanding of the world. As a result scientific disciplines such as history, physics emerged which tried to locate the subject in the construction of time-where history looked at the collation of events which stitch up together to give the idea of a collective past and physics on the other hand shifted its focus to study the world as being created as a component of matter,

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collected through ages. As the centuries progressed we see this idea of studying the temporality gaining pre-eminence.

With the turn of the twentieth century it became the zeitgeist in itself. Popularly hailed as the modernist period and largely characterized by advanced experimentation in arts and aesthetics, apart from the rise of colonialism and bourgeois capitalism, the era witnessed the haunting question of studying the time. The shock of the First World War had not waned when the world saw another World War and the complete annihilation of habitats of living for certain countries. The preoccupation with space started to be consolidated at this period.

It was in Michel Foucault's seminal essay, 'Of Other Spaces: Utopias and Heterotopias' (originally published as 'Des espaces autres') that the idea becomes clear and well established. As he aptly remarks:

The great obsession of the nineteenth century was, as we know, history: with its themes of development and of suspension, of crisis, and cycle, themes of the ever-accumulating past, with its great preponderance of dead men and the menacing glaciation of the world. The present epoch will perhaps be above all the epoch of space. We are in the epoch of simultaneity: we are in the epoch of juxtaposition, the epoch of the near and far, of the side-by-side, of the dispersed.¹

It was Foucault who turned the philosophical gaze completely and prioritized space over time. Foucault's idea is predicated on the foundation of 'simultaneity' and 'juxtaposition' which seeks to wriggle out of the stranglehold of time and assert the individuality of its own existence. Thus space is not treated as barren, unproductive, fruitless, desolate and sterile; rather, it pronounces its fecundity triumphantly asking a reinvestigation of the relations formed hitherto. Space is not a concomitant of time. It is not a by-product of the historical material conditions of living as traditional Marxists

would argue. Space becomes the dominant cultural idiom of foregrounding the relation of experience crisscrossed in the map of time which is connected and bound by its relations.

With the advent of globalization the necessity of forging relations was accelerated by the rise in technology. The world-wide web swathed the entire globe in its foray and the 'dot com' bubble spawned the birth of a new media culture erected on the scaffolds of late capitalism, where 'image' asserted itself over the real. The nature of this new form of capitalism was significantly different from the hitherto historical epochs in not just the method of the production of the commodity but in its way of creating new markets of its own. Economic liberalization was earmarked with flows of transnational capital and establishing new territories of power and appropriating newer world cultures. This new form of capitalism does not have a territorial center of power and does not rely on fixed boundaries or barriers. Hardt and Negri in their book *Empire* call this new set of power as 'decentered and deterritorializing apparatus of rule that progressively incorporates the entire global realm within its open, expanding frontiers.'² It is no more fixed and rooted to a specific epicenter. Instead the nodes spread out far and wide. The very nature of this power is fluid, extraneous and variegated. Once again as Negri and Hardt write:

In the postmodernization of the global economy, the creation of wealth tends ever more toward what we call biopolitical production, the production of social life itself, in which, the economic, the political, and the cultural increasingly overlap and invest each other.³

Therefore the reprioritization of space has become the need of the hour. Imperialism has shape-shifted in the post-capital scenario which seeks to conquer new spaces in the form of newer markets; the space of the new media which projects such incessant flow of information and transactions; the space of the digital and the cyber world wherein identities are replicated endlessly; and last but not the

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least, the space around our everyday life. All of these form unique points of interaction which collectively govern the very nature of our existence. We need to be critically aware of such heterogeneous, multifarious and divergent relational variability of experience which creates the idea of this space. A tendency of capitalism is to disregard these discontinuities, ruptures in the spatiality, treating it as a homogenized single entity trying to constantly reiterate a reified idea of global ‘oneness’. However this suffers from a dangerous essentialism and needs to be reinvestigated. The present paper starts from this critical juncture of thought where an effort will be made to investigate the spatial relations particularly inflected by the idea of late capitalism and ascendancy of media culture. I would take up two novels of Don De Lillo – *White Noise* (1985) ⁴ and *Cosmopolis* (2003) ⁵ and would argue the influence of the shifts and patterns in capital and their impact on the central protagonists of the novel to indicate how individuals battle against the global boom of a media-saturated society and how the superfluity of consumption dents a hole in their personal imagination. The main locus of the problem is in the spatial tensions imbued in these two novels.

It was Gaston Bachelard who first took up the subject of space in his book, *The Poetics of Space* (1958) ⁶ where he put on a phenomenologist’s perspective and tried to imagine the inhabited space out of the geometrical space. Remaining largely restricted in the household space, Bachelard’s idea of topoanalysis (‘the systematic psychological study of the sites of our intimate lives’) ⁷ has been extensively used by later social scientists. The imaginative association which Bachelard invests in space, tries to eke out the hidden stories in the everyday space of the house and render it a poetic understanding. But the political reorganization of space – space can be studied as a systemic discursive pattern to observe the strategies of the effects of globalization – was discussed by Henri Lefebvre in his book *The Production of Space*. It was the critical turn that was necessary and space was looked upon as the fundamental

revelation of a glaring disparity – the two cultures of the bourgeois and the proletariat. Primarily focusing on the architectural shifts in designs and patterns, the book scrutinized the logic of globalization and the economic welfare theory posited by the West and the impact of such an unequal distribution of wealth on the Third World nations. Globalization began to be looked upon as a trickle-down effect where the First World nations reaped rewards at the cost of the exploitation of the marginalized. New spaces were produced both in the cityscape as well as outside it clearly demarcating the establishment of newer territories of power. As Lefebvre would argue:

Though a product to be used, to be consumed, it is also a means of production; networks of exchange and flows of raw material and energy fashion space and are determined by it. Thus this means of production, produced as such cannot be separated either from the productive forces, including technology and knowledge, or from the social division of labour which shapes it, or from the state or the superstructure of the society.⁸

This was followed by Edward Soja and his categorical interventionist strategy to puncture the idea of modernization and how the unevenness of it has restructured and reshaped the spatial understanding. Borrowing the postmodernist framework, Soja in his *Postmodern Geographies* links spatial changes with the advancement of capitalism; handcuffing historicity with the geopolitics and how both are being imbricated in each other he demonstrates a problem. Soja remarks:

We must be insistently aware of how space can be made to hide consequences from us, how relations of power and discipline are inscribed into the apparently innocent spatiality of social life, how human geographies become filled with politics and ideology.⁹

Doreen Massey, another geographer and theorist of space reiterates the idea of space as 'contemporaneous existence' and harps on the

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coevalness of space and the ‘relational’ experience of the Being in the world. The inextricable link between space, urbanization and political injustice is exemplified in David Harvey’s *Social Justice and the City*:

Space and political organization of space express social relationships but also react back upon them... Industrialization once the product of urbanism, is now being produced by it... When we use the words ‘urban revolution’ we designate the total ensemble of transformations which run throughout contemporary society and which bring about a change from a period in which questions of economic growth and industrialization predominate to the period in which urban problematic becomes decisive.¹⁰

Our aim is to understand the polyvalent nature of this political space, the gaps that it produces and the production of this space under the global overarching halo of late capitalism. Along with the spatial theories, we propose to use the tool of postmodern criticism developed by Fredric Jameson and Jean Baudrillard in our study of DeLillo’s novels to be reassessed in terms of spatial consciousness.

DeLillo’s novels have garnered widespread critical acclaim among the readers. As a quintessential postmodern novelist, DeLillo’s novels have focused on the rise of technology, the apogee of media culture and a growing insecurity of living in such a world fraught with tension. The focus of the argument will be to show how such times have shaped up the space around us and how it is being reflected in the novels. I would like to begin the analysis from *White Noise* (1985) and would gradually proceed to *Cosmopolis* (2003) and would try to establish a changing pattern by locating the shift in the spatial consciousness.

White Noise begins with the response of Jack Gladney faced with the perpetual dread about his own existence in the wake of a fast changing world. The setting is a remote College-on-the Hill where

Gladney is introduced as the Professor of Hitler Studies. It is interesting to observe that Jack's inhabited space changes rapidly from the beginning of the novel. Apparently innocuous in its setting, the first part of the novel 'Waves and Radiation' predicts the effect of living in a highly technologized society and the effect of living in a world dominated by media culture and saturation. The space of the consumer society continually creates more desires so that men are all thrust into a world of instability; flux comes to the fore when Alphonse Stompanato, Chair of the Department of American Environments at the College on the Hill declares: 'We are suffering from brain fade. We need an occasional catastrophe to break the incessant bombardment of information.'¹¹

If space is the invisible network of relations forged at a given time then this relation in the postindustrial society is ineluctably forged with the rising use of technology. There emanates a point of interface between the two worlds – the human and the machine. There are many such instances in the novel which is predicated upon this problem. In one of this we encounter Jack going out in the morning to withdraw money from an Automated Teller Machine and feels:

Waves of relief and gratitude flowed over me. The system had blessed my life. I felt its support and approval. The system hardware, the mainframe sitting in a locked room in some distant city. What a pleasing interaction. I sensed that something of deep personal value, but not money, not that at all, had been authenticated and confirmed... The networks, the circuits, the streams, the harmonies.¹²

The endless production of the social space by the media culture infiltrates the very world of the private and the individual gets reduced to a minute speck, a mere dot which is gobbled up by the narrative of the capital. The body becomes the site where the data plays on, the schism between the image and the real being seldom understood. Murray Jay Siskind, Jack Gladney's colleague at the college offers an explanation in his brilliant summation:

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You have to learn how to look. You have to open yourself to the data. TV offers incredible amounts of psychic data... Look at the wealth of data concealed in the grid, in the bright packaging, the jingles, the slice-of-life messages and endless repetitions, like chants and mantras. 'Coke is it, Coke is it, Coke is it.'¹³

Jean Baudrillard, the French sociologist associated with the idea of pronouncing the triumph of the image over the real in the postmodern world would describe such a situation as, 'When the real is no longer what it was, nostalgia assumes its full meaning.'¹⁴ The image is now not just a replica of the real but has a life of its own and can survive without the real through its innumerable replications. The subject is caught in this space of the image, appropriated in the facts and appended in the vast network of the 'hyperreal'. The being outgrows the space of the virtual and it soon spreads everywhere unevenly. Babette, wife of Jack Gladney goes to the church to take her class. Once when she is spotted on the camera without her notice, the action gets a life of its own:

It was the picture that mattered, the face in black and white, animated but also flat, distanced, sealed off, timeless. It was but wasn't her...she was coming into being, endlessly being formed and reformed as the muscles in her face worked at smiling and speaking as the electronic dots swarmed.

We were being shot through with Babette. Her image was projected on our bodies, swam in us and through us. Babette of electrons and protons, of whatever forces produced that gray light we took to be her face.¹⁵

The space of the 'now' is made up of the economic, social and cultural shifts and shocks. Technology has infiltrated this private space so deep that it is very difficult to extricate oneself completely out of this. Stacey Olster in her analysis of the novel talked about this "intersubjectivity" of being as:

Just how that “we” have come to be constituted and whether there remains any ground for recovering an “I” of individual subjectivity in such a climate are issues at the heart of Don DeLillo's *White Noise* (1985). They inform not only the acts of DeLillo's protagonist, a college professor forced to realize that he is just every man in any city, but also the task faced by DeLillo himself, namely, finding a critical position from which to delineate a cultural phenomenon without being wholly absorbed by it.¹⁶

With the spread of the mysterious Air Borne Toxic Event we will see a collapse of the national and international boundaries, and the coevalness, the simultaneity of living is invoked in the face of a threat to existence. Initially Jack will dismiss the threat to his own self as ‘society is set up in such a way that it's the poor and the uneducated who suffer the main impact of natural and man-made disasters’¹⁷ and not the middle class and intellectually gifted people like him. He presumes that ‘these things don't happen in places like Blacksmith’ but only in places with ‘mobile homes out in the scrubby parts of the county’¹⁸ These notions will soon be squashed. Fredric Jameson has argued postmodernism as a condition which is a sort of ‘weakening of “historicity” both in our relationship to public History and in the new form of our private temporality.’¹⁹ One sees that Gladney too feels a structural dislocatedness in the vast array of history around him. The space of history is multiplying rapidly as a storehouse of data, facts, integers and numbers which control his existence, making him ‘a sum total of your data.’²⁰ The SIMUVAC (Simulated Evacuation) rescue team member informs him:

Its what we call a massive data base tally. Gladney, J.A.K. I punch in the name, the substance, the exposure time and then I tap into your computer history, Your genetics, your personals, your medicals, your psychological, your place- and –hospitals.²¹

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In the postmodern context space gets crucially changed as the individual battles with the ever-changing terrain of the present. Media is controlled by capital and as everything is saleable:

[W]hen death is rendered graphically, is televised so to speak, that you sense an eerie separation between your condition and yourself. A network of symbols has been introduced, an entire awesome technology wrested from the gods. It makes you feel a stranger in your own dying.²²

The state sells the fear and watches at it imperturbably making Murray Jay Siskind tell Jack, ‘This is the nature of modern death. It has a life independent of us.’²³

Perhaps the best understanding of the dominance of the new spatial logic of capitalism comes from a reading of DeLillo’s *Cosmopolis* (2003) written just after the aftermath of the September 9/11 terrorist attack on the Twin Towers of the United States. Eric Packer, the hero of the novel who is a multi-billionaire represents that class of the neo-liberal business magnets of America whose empire of wealth stretches across the international boundaries. The largeness of his empire emblazons the idea of the accumulation of wealth in a few hands and harks on the inequity of globalization. The novel centers on his choice to go outside his ‘forty-eight room mansion’ to get a haircut. There are limousines stretched in rows outside. At the very outset, the sprawling space of his personal house reeks of the smell of this inequality and the unequal distribution of wealth, as well as he gleams with the view of a perfect technocrat:

He walked through the apartment, forty-eight rooms. He did this when he felt hesitant and depressed, striding past the lap pool, the card parlour, the gymnasium, past the shark tank and screening room. He stopped at the borzoi pen and talked to his dogs. Then he went to the annex, where there were currencies to track and research reports to examine.²⁴

The building was of ‘eighty-nine stories’ and was ‘nine hundred feet

high, the tallest residential tower in the world, a commonplace oblong whose only statement was its size.' The spatiality of his existence exudes the aura of confidence:

The tower gave him strength and depth. He knew what he wanted, a haircut, but stood a while longer in the soaring noise of the street and studied the mass and scale of the tower... He scanned the length and felt connected to it, sharing the surface and the environment that came into contact with the surface, from both sides. A surface separates inside from out and belongs no less to one than the other.²⁵

The predominant concern of Eric is his investment in the dollars against the yen and the entire novel pirouettes against this. His cross-town route on 47th Street in Manhattan takes him from his residence in the international district near United Nations headquarters and the Japan Society on First Avenue, threading past Times Square and the Nasdaq Centre to the south, and reaching the industrial lofts, tenements, and an underground garage past Eleventh Avenue; from dawn to nightfall; and from the bastions of wealth and global power to the squalid indigence of an abandoned warehouse – this novel takes shape like a personal odyssey and gives us a broad understanding of the changing places. Wearing his dark glasses, Eric Packer represented the face of the faceless transnational capital that circulates globally. And as Fredric Jameson explains, 'this whole global, yet American, postmodern culture is the internal and superstructural expression of a whole new wave of American military and economic domination throughout the world.'²⁶

Eric Packer is the lord of this domain, the very avatar of cyber capital who wants to ensure the utmost security of his 'system'. The route is impeded by the movement of the President of the United States who, as Torval, his security guard informs, is about to take the same road which he will take. It is interesting to observe that Packer

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no longer deals in mere stock predictions or commercial production pertaining to a particular business or trade. His concern is solely dedicated towards charting and predicting the movement of money itself, seeking the “hidden rhythms in the fluctuation of a given currency.”²⁷ The space which he inhabits is enmeshed in the technology, “there were medleys of data on every screen, all flowing symbols and alpine charts, the polychrome numbers pulsing.”²⁸ There is the ‘patterns, ratios, indexes, whole maps of information’ which echoes the concerns of Gladney’s acceptance of his helplessness in *White Noise*. The constant interaction between technology and capital, ‘the aesthetics of interaction,’²⁹ the inseparability has cast a shadow on the personal space which no longer stays as personal. It is the market which exercised its control over the subjects. As Eric’s financial analyst Vija Kinski states that it is in no way possible for an individual to “exist outside the market.”³⁰ There is a sort of sardonic banter in her voice when she tells Eric looking at the screens flashing the continuous rise and fall of exchange rates in Eric’s car, ‘The glow of the screens. I love the screens. The glow of cybercapital. So radiant and seductive.’³¹

Just as the nature of modern death has changed in *White Noise*, the nature of modern capital too has undergone a transformation. Marx had long before compared Capital as part of the undead, nosferatu which comes back again and again to haunt us. In this post-capitalist world money has taken a new turn. Vija Kinski’s words sound prophetic when she claims, ‘Money is talking to itself.’³² As they traverse around the other side of Broadway, they could get a partial view of the electronic display of the market information, the moving message units that streaked across the face of an office tower. The space is characterized by the incessant flow of information so much so that the condition becomes saturated ‘brain fade’ in *White Noise*, till something unexpected punctures it and instills the notion of a catastrophe. At this point the narrative gets ruptured by the sudden news of the death of Nikolai Kaganovich, which creates the illusion

of a catastrophe. Kaganovich was also a multi-billionaire from Russia like Eric who was found murdered outside his dacha. The very nature of the transnational flow of capital is once again exemplified when we see that Kaganovich was 'a man of swaggering wealth and shady reputation, owner of Russia's largest media conglomerate,' and his stakes would range from 'sex magazines' to 'satellite operations.'

Urbanization was a product of the project of enlightenment. It was taken up by the major nation states after the Second World War to build up a robust economic structure. Yet this urbanization became the profound centre of paradox and the growth of the modern cities exemplifies this. New York, the geospatial centre in this novel is also moored in such ambiguities. The visions experienced by Eric on his way become the objective gaze of the audience as they map the changing contours of underdevelopment. In one particular section of the novel, Eric saw a group of tourists moving in swirls and drifts, 'shuffling in and out of megastores and circling vendors' carts.' What strikes the reader is the dehumanized existence and the mark of squalor in their appearance:

Eric watched them cross the street, stunted humans in the shadow of the underwear gods that adorned the soaring billboards. These were figures beyond gender and procreation, enchanted women in men's shorts, beyond commerce, even, men immortal in their muscle tone, in the clustered bulge at the crotchline.³³

David Harvey cites this as 'accumulation by dispossession' in his book *Cosmopolitanism and the Geographies of Freedom*, where he writes, 'the net worth of 358 richest people in the world was then (during the period of the 1990's) found to be equal to the combined income of the poorest 45 per cent of the world's population- 2.3 billion people.'³⁴ This is the present state of the post-capital scenario and this is leading to the condition of a global crisis. This accumulation by dispossession creates the situation of a global crisis

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as newer spaces are encroached upon for the creation of newer markets for the capitalists which leads to as Harvey says, ‘a predatory accumulation practice’:

These include the commodification and privatization of land and labour power, and the forceful expulsion of peasant populations from the land (as in Mexico and in India in recent times); conversion of various forms of property rights (common, collective, state) into exclusive private property rights; suppression of rights to the commons, suppression of alternative (indigenous) forms of production and consumption, appropriation of assets (including natural resources); the slave trade (which continues today, particularly in the sex industry); usury; and , most devastating of all, the use of the credit system and debt entrapment to acquire the assets of the others, most dramatically represented by the mortgage foreclosures that swept through the United States housing market beginning in 2006.³⁵

Towards the end of Part I of *Cosmopolis* we see a clear reflection of this crisis, when Eric’s limousine passes Times Square and crosses Broadway from the East side to the West side of Manhattan, they are thwarted by violent demonstrations held by red and black clad anarchists at the Nasdaq Exchange, trading floor for technology stocks in the new economy. The notion of a false sense of security with which the novel started, which has sort of cocooned the world of the capitalists, the wealthy class from the real situation, bursts into smithereens. The loud cry of the protesters rings in the air, ‘A specter is haunting the world. The specter of Capitalism.’³⁶ The line echoes the first sentence used by Marx in *The Communist Manifesto*, albeit with a difference. Kinski sounds more of a Baudrillardian simulacrum when she says that this entropic condition is produced by the ‘free market. These people are a fantasy generated by the market itself’ and that “they do not exist outside the market.”³⁷ The culture of consumption has been so internalized that the

demonstrators are at once a product and a by-product of this system of production. It is for the market's need that they exist and they are essentially "marketdriven". Their existence therefore can be the summative produce of all the global markets. That is why such demonstrations of protest too come with a face value which gets exchanged in the market. So when a protestor immolates himself in a fit of rage, the system quickly interpellates him and rejects him at once. It becomes a 'shadow of transaction between the demonstrators and the state.' To Eric and to Kinski the protest becomes 'a form of systemic hygiene, purging and lubricating. It attested again and again, for the ten thousandth time, to the market culture's innovative brilliance, its ability to shape itself to its own flexible needs, absorbing everything around it.'³⁸

The market culture which appropriates everyone is the terrible drive let loose by the capitalists. It becomes so addictive that it starts haunting the inventors at times. This is what happens at the time when Eric becomes conscious of his own death at the hands of his stalker Benno Levin. But instead of finding remorse and pain he wished to transgress his mortality and unite with the digital, the information, numbers and live in the disks which stores data with the possibility open for endless repetitions of his life and death.

The idea was to live outside the given limits, in a chip, on a disk, as data, in whirl, in radiant spin, a consciousness saved from void. The technology was imminent or not. It was semi-mythical. It was the natural next step. It would never happen. It is happening now; an evolutionary advance that needed only the practical mapping of the nervous system onto digital memory. It would be the master thrust of cyber-capital, to extend the human experience toward infinity as a medium for corporate growth and investment, for the accumulation of profits and vigorous reinvestment.³⁹

Thus DeLillo's *Cosmopolis* depicts the collapse of the American

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future determined by the pure synergy of finance and technology and proclaims a warning for the future as well. Alongside this it also becomes an indicting commentary on the changing relationalities around, the complex dynamics of relationships forged and wrought under the spirit of late capitalism. Both the novels strategically call for a reorientation of the ‘structures of feeling’ as Raymond Williams suggests, urging us to re-question our position in this world. At the same time renewed spatial consciousness enables one to assess the unevenness of the cultural domains which we all share. The two novels link to this idea of the fractured spaces both the individual as well as the social brilliantly. It is to this space that we must turn back again and again for it seems to be dangerous and fraught with all the contradictions.

Endnotes :

- ¹ Michel Foucault, ‘Of Other Spaces: Utopias and Heterotopias’, *Architecture/Movement/Continuite*, 5 (October 1984): 46-49.
- ² Antonio Negri and Michael Hardt. *Empire* (Massachusetts: Harvard University Press, 2000), p. xii.
- ³ Negri and Hardt. *Empire*, p. xiii.
- ⁴ Don DeLillo, *White Noise* (New York: Viking Penguin, 1984)
- ⁵ Don DeLillo, *Cosmopolis* (New York: Scribner, 2003).
- ⁶ Gaston Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space: The Classic Look at How We Experience Intimate Places* (Boston: Beacon Press, 1958).
- ⁷ Bachelard, *The Poetics of Space*, p.9.
- ⁸ Henri Lefebvre, *The Production of Space* (Cambridge: Basil Blackwell, 1974), p. 85.
- ⁹ Edward Soja, *Postmodern Geographies: The Reassertion of Space in Critical Social Theory* (London: Verso, 1989), p. 6.
- ¹⁰ David Harvey, *Social Justice and the City* (Athens, Georgia: The University of Georgia Press, 1973) p. 306.
- ¹¹ DeLillo, *White Noise* (New York: Viking Penguin, 1984), p. 66.
- ¹² DeLillo, *White Noise*, p. 55.
- ¹³ DeLillo, *White Noise*, p. 61.

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- ¹⁴ Jean Baudrillard, *Simulations* (New York: Semiotext(e), 1983), p. 6.
- ¹⁵ DeLillo, *White Noise*, p. 124.
- ¹⁶ Stacey Olster, 'White Noise' in *The Cambridge Companion to Don DeLillo*, ed. John N. Duvall (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008), p. 79.
- ¹⁷ DeLillo, *White Noise*, p. 133.
- ¹⁸ DeLillo, *White Noise*, p. 133-134.
- ¹⁹ Fredric Jameson, *Postmodernism, or, The Cultural Logic of Late Capitalism* (Durham: Duke University Press, 1991), p. 5.
- ²⁰ DeLillo, *White Noise*, p. 165.
- ²¹ DeLillo, *White Noise*, p. 165.
- ²² DeLillo, *White Noise*, p. 165.
- ²³ DeLillo, *White Noise*, p. 175.
- ²⁴ DeLillo, *Cosmopolis* (New York: Scribner, 2003), p. 2.
- ²⁵ DeLillo, *Cosmopolis*, p. 2.
- ²⁶ Jameson, *Postmodernism, or, The Cultural Logic of Late Capitalism*, p. 5.
- ²⁷ DeLillo, *Cosmopolis*, p. 4.
- ²⁸ DeLillo, *Cosmopolis*, p. 4.
- ²⁹ DeLillo, *Cosmopolis*, p. 33.
- ³⁰ DeLillo, *Cosmopolis*, p. 30.
- ³¹ DeLillo, *Cosmopolis*, p. 30.
- ³² DeLillo, *Cosmopolis*, p. 30.
- ³³ DeLillo, *Cosmopolis*, p. 32.
- ³⁴ David Harvey, *Cosmopolitanism and the Geographies of Freedom* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2009), p. 58.
- ³⁵ Harvey, *Cosmopolitanism and the Geographies of Freedom*, p. 68.
- ³⁶ DeLillo, *Cosmopolis*, p. 37.
- ³⁷ DeLillo, *Cosmopolis*, p. 35.
- ³⁸ DeLillo, *Cosmopolis*, p. 39.
- ³⁹ DeLillo, *Cosmopolis*, p. 80.